

1 **Systems biologic identification of HPV E7 functions.**

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6 A complete description of papillomavirus E7 functions and network interaction partners remains elusive.
7 We demonstrate here activation of the kinase *Clk2* in cells containing ectopic expression of E7.
8 Concomitant with CLK2 kinase induction by E7 was activation of the phosphatase *Acp2*. ACP2 activation
9 was accompanied by *Ppp3r1* silencing which was likely compensatory. The transcriptomic data revealed
10 E7 contribution to growth factor signal transduction in cancer.

11 Citations

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